

DIFFERENT TRAITS DETERMINE INTRODUCTION, NATURALIZATION AND INVASION SUCCESS - PROTEACEAE AS A TEST CASE

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Introduction

Proteaceae is an interesting group to explore traits of invasiveness because plants have been introduced widely and comprise species with different invasion status. This study aimed to identify traits correlated to introduction, naturalization and invasion success.

Materials and Methods

Created a global database of introduced, naturalized and invasive species, collected information on various species traits, and used boosted regression trees to analyse the link between the different invasion barriers.

Results

Species with larger home ranges, dispersed by wind, low susceptibility to phytophthora, resprouts and large seeds all had a higher probability of naturalizing. Plants used as barriers, tall in stature, large home ranges, small seed mass, serotinous and re-seeds after a fire successfully invaded.

Proteaceae invasion status globally

Conclusions

Some variables show similar selection at both stages, other variables are only selected at one stage and some show selection in differing directions as invasion progresses. For some variables there is a clear mechanistic role at play, but for others this remains to be determined.

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